

Sustainability and Environmental Ethics: The ways of overcoming crises of the Human Society

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Abstract

In the present time world is facing an unprecedented danger. Many peoples in different countries on the globe have been infected and dead by the effect of different viruses, diseases, pollutions etc. Social development, human health (mental & Physical), global economy and environment have been affected by different issues in present time. Many threats have engulfed this world through lot of issues such as terrorism, imperialist aggression, trade war, hunger, pollution, intolerance, virus attack etc. In the face of all these threats, world economy and social development have been collapsed. As a result, the sustainable development is often hampered. In this paper I will address the issues, which are the responsible for creating threats to the world. I will try to find out the ways for solving these issues and to make a healthy beautiful world. We need to work for sustainable development by giving the equal importance to the economic development, social development and environmental development. In this connection I will briefly discuss different dimension of sustainable developments especially of economic, social and environmental development and how to be established it globally. It will be possible to make a beautiful and peaceful world by solving various problems through sustainable development.

Key words

Sustainability, environmental ethics, intrinsic value, social welfare, equity, diversity, ecocentrism, anthropocentrism

Introduction

In the present time world is facing an unprecedented danger. Many peoples in different countries on the globe have been infected and dead by the effect of different viruses attack, diseases, pollutions etc. Social development, human health (mental & Physical), global economy and environment have been affected by different issues in present time. For the long time human beings claimed themselves as the master, who are the most intelligent and best species in the world. But now they are helpless with confronting different unprecedented issues like deadly virus, diseases, pollutions etc. These enemies did not come overnight. If we look at the long history of the development of human civilization, we can invent, that in the name of development, humans have arbitrarily extinct the plants, animals and natural resources. Resulted, increased air pollution, water pollution, noise pollution - the whole environment has been polluted. Human intervention over the natural environment has demolished the natural beauty and diversity of the ecosystem. Diversity is a systematic relation where every living organism with a single ecosystem or Habitat including numbers and diversity of species and all environmental aspects. The domination and exploitation attitudes of human being not only applied towards nonhuman world, but also this attitude spread to own species. This violent selfish attitudes have greatly increased the possibility for appearing the crisis in the human society. Many threats have engulfed this world through lot of issues such as terrorism, Imperialist aggression, trade war, hunger, pollution, intolerance, virus attack etc. In the face of all these threats, the economy, society and the environment have been collapsed. As a result, the sustainable development is often hampered. There are many challenges in front of sustainable development in today's world. People are not getting the basic needs for survive. Different countries are waging war by creating a war situation through the policy of imperialist aggression for economic prosperity and enriching various lethal weapons. And also inequalities in different castes, religions, sexes are threats to sustainable development. We need to work for sustainable development of economy, society and environment and balance them with equal importance.

Sustainability is the way to minimize different threats in the society:

There is a large amount of disagreement about in thinking of sustainability. there are some possibilities to consider of the sustainability, like; a rate of economic growth, a level of happiness, a rate of extinction, a rate of consumption, a level of wealth, a level of biodiversity, a particular set of ecosystem services, or a way of life etc. Removal of hunger is the big challenge to the third world country like Asia, Africa, and Latin America. The populations are being over crowded in the world today. Consumptions of natural resources are rapidly increasing to peoples. Humans are destroying trees, deforestation, water lands and build industries for providing foods needs of the peoples. it is very difficult in the world removal of hunger in pollution free environment. Malthus explained *in his writings: An Essay on the Principle of Population* "... population, when unchecked, increased in a geometrical ratio, and subsistence for man in an arithmetical ratio."¹

We must growth our economy for the needs of the increased people of the world. The main thing is the explosion of populations may affect the stability of the sustainability or sustainable development of the world.

It is the challenge to the world how to established economic sustainability with maintain sustained environment? Natural resources are one of the major foundation of the sustainability. Though the peoples have started the procedure for restoring natural resources and life support system for the people. The way of productions have huge changed with less environmental damages. The issues of sustainability has been made a part of global politics. Even the sustainable practices are followed by local, regional and globally. With limit of the natural resources society's development for long time is known as sustainable development.. The concept of 'Sustainable development' officially appeared to global society in "Our Common Future" by the World Commission on Environment and Development, in 1987. The Chairperson of the Commission was Gro Harlem Brundtland, the former Prime Minister of Norway. Sustainability or sustainable development deals and manages the impacts on patterns of environmental degradation and human development. Sustainable development will protect environment and economy with compromising of environmental policy and institutional policy. It helps economy and environment to be healthy, develop and improve living conditions. The concept 'sustainability' or 'sustainable development' is defined in the Bruntland Report "*humanity has the ability to make development sustainable to ensure that it meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs*".² Sustainability has three main dimensions; economy dimension, *socio-political* Dimension and environmental dimension.

Economy Dimension:

Economic sustainability is most important approach that ensure and provides economic welfare to the future generation. Unsustainable economic development could bring unprecedented situations where economic growth can be less or reduced even to zero. Economic sustainability is important for human society.it maintain the natural resources and capital for required commodity to the society and its people. It depends on different sectors, policies an areas, like energy, water, fishery, agriculture, forestry etc. The policy of economic sustainability is to find out the cost, benefits, strength and the externalities in the society and with apply the technologies bring to the society more efficient outcome from less efficient outcome for the social welfare. A social welfare system is a regular set up to help citizens of a country at different stages of their lives. The system is arise by the government or organization as usually for the benefit of the society. It supply necessary things to the citizen. It is an ongoing process which means taking care of the specific needs of the society. Distribute the resources, the balance between growth and consumption, to assume the limited natural resources, and it believe that economic growth can be able to provide goods and necessary resources to the peoples and the growth of economic development to be continued. It deals the impact of the economic conditions on the stakeholders at globally, nationally and locally throughout the society. Economy of the human society is an important part of sustainable development or sustainability. It not only manage environmental issues, but it deals with natural resources, human-made resources and human capital, which develop both economy and society. It maintain the natural resources and capital for required commodity to the society and its people. Economic sustainability is a development that must include human rights, needs and responsibility toward environment. Economic efficiency, equity, and environmental sustainability are playing main role for achieving sustainable development.

Socio-Political Dimension:

Social sustainability aims to preserve social capital for the sufficient as per needs of the future generation of our society with maintain the requirement of the present time. Socio-ethical sustainability maintain the relation to the duty and responsibility to the peoples of the communities, cultures and globalisation. It focuses on maintaining and improving social quality with concepts such as cohesion, reciprocity and honesty and the importance of relationships amongst people. . Social sustainability includes lot of issues in the society. Social sustainability deals with the notions of equity, empowerment, cultural identity accessibility, participation and institutional stability etc. It tries to alleviation of poverty with growth of economy and the same time it preserve the environment. It ensure human rights, equality, preservation of cultural identity, gender, cast, races, religion, involuntary resettlement, poverty reduction, etc. the environmental sustainability is to be necessary pre-condition of sustained economic growth and sustained social development. We have the responsibility to people who have no place of residence and are not residents of any country. Whether it is Rohingya crisis or enclave people or people who have been oppressed and deported from different countries. Everyone must be given the rights of a citizen. However, it is not possible for any one country. In that case, the leaders of all countries must take responsibility and recognize these helpless people as citizens and give them the rights of citizens. In the 21st century, imagine people who have no country, food, clothing and shelter is like a slap in the face of our developed society. Political leaders and social workers have to make different political decisions, laws and to be enacted for restoring the lifestyle and citizenship of peoples who are homeless, cloth less, poor, country less. The members of the society should behave fraternal among themselves. Social development may possible through Socio-political development.

Environmental Dimension:

Our daily life of present and the future generations are depending on the long-term functioning of the ecosystem and its natural resources, like, energy, water, air, all raw materials of the nature in environment. The concept 'environmental sustainability' has emerged from the observation of the importance of the raw materials of the environment for long-time availability to the generation to generation of humans. It deals integrity of ecosystem, carrying capacity and biodiversity. Environmental sustainability aims to improve human welfare through the protection of natural capital (e.g. land, air, water, minerals etc.)

Human should avoid disturbance regionally and globally to the ecosystem. Human activities should be limited within the circle that is allowed by the ecosystem. Natural capital are water, air, minerals, energy, space, those are essential for life. The interactions and relationships between these elements become sustain ecosystem which is possible present knowledge and technologies. He process of artificially produced resources are expensive and insufficient, even these procedure pollute environment badly. Environment contribute to the human life and human economy through environmental functions. The concept of 'environmental functions' were entered in economy by Hueting (1980). De Groot (1992) developed the concept and define it as 'the capacity of natural processes and components to provide goods and services that

satisfy human needs'.³ Human ways of life are being sustained by the help of environmental sustainability, which is also provide the necessary resources to the economy for maintain economic welfare to the human society. Environmental sustainability derives the public polices, like individual species maintenance, balanced of mutual relationship with other living beings are maintaining the ecological system properly. The impacts of Environment spread to global, continental, (bio) regional, national and local levels. Generally. We do not have any right to drain the natural resources, those are necessary for needs of future generations. The principle of equity states "*in a sustainable framework, every person, including those from future generations, has the right to the same environmental space, that is, the right to access the same amount of natural resources*".⁴

Environmental ethics and sustainability:

Environmental ethics is defined as the moral relationship between humans and the natural environment. It concern with the value and morality related issues of the personal, relational and policy level. There are many principles of environmental ethics. Mainly two important theories of environmental ethics are anthropocentric worldview and ecocentric worldview. Usually every development in the society is anthropocentric, which is done in the interest of human being. Anthropocentrism is derived from Ancient Greek words *ánthrōpos*, "human being"; and "center" that belief human beings are the most important entity in the universe. It belief that world is defined valuable in favour of human interest and humans are only conqueror in the universe. In anthropocentric view people believe that they were given right to dominate over plants, animals or all members of nonhuman world. Humans are the sole bearers of intrinsic value and non-human world contains instrumental value. Nonhuman entities exist for serving humans needs.. The anthropocentric perception is responsible for the environmental crisis as people build houses by destroying forests, killing others species resulted the loss of biological diversity, global warming etc. Therefore it is difficult to social establish sustainability in true sense. In order to establish realistic sustainability, we have to go beyond human-centered environmental thinking. We have to acknowledge intrinsic value of environment. The development should be established by following of the ecocentric world view of environmental ethics.

Sentientism was the first effort by Jeremy Bentham to overcome anthropocentric world view and to extend moral consideration to all sentient being. He says "*The question is not can they reason? Nor, can they talk? But can they suffer?*"⁵ Only The capacity for suffering criterion is the essential characteristic for entitling sentient being to equal consideration of moral interests. Another effort of moral responsibility extended from human to living being has been done by Paul W. Taylor (1981). He says that we should protect all life in nature. He argued in Biocentrism that humans should extend the moral duties to all living being in the planet, as they are interconnected in the ecosystems. Taylor lays out his ideas for Biocentrism in four main components

1. Humans are s members of the Earth's community of life, and the same condition to be applied for all non-human members (i.e. humans share the same value as all other living beings).

2. All members of earth community are interconnected elements in the ecosystem.
3. Each individual organism is conceived of as a teleological centre of life, pursuing its own good in its own way
4. Humans are not superior to other species, the thought of human superiority is an irrational biased.

We can see the same arguments in the Land Ethic by Aldo Leopold. His famous work “A Sand County Almanac”, where he mentioned “*the role of Homo sapiens from conqueror of the land-community to plain member and citizen of it. It implies respect for his fellow-members, and also respect for the community as such.*”⁶ He claimed that the moral consideration to be extend to the land community. He hold the principle “*A thing is right when it tends to preserve the integrity, stability, and beauty of the biotic community. It is wrong when it tends otherwise*”⁷. Finally we got deep ecological principles to the environment by George Sessions and Arne Naess (1984).

The policies of environmental science are concerned only in part with pollution and resource depletion. But deep ecological principles of environmental ethic are deeper concerns which touch upon principles of The well-being and flourishing of human and nonhuman life on Earth have value in themselves it doesn't depend on human .

2. Richness and diversity of life forms contribute to the realization of these values.
3. Humans have no right to reduce this richness and diversity except to satisfy vital needs.
4. Present human interference over nonhuman world is excessive, and the situation is rapidly worsening.
5. The flourishing of human life and cultures is compatible with a substantial decrease of the human population. Decrease of human population requires for the flourishing of nonhuman life.
6. Policies must therefore be changed. The changes in policies affect ideological structures, basic economic and technological. The resulting state of affairs will be deeply different from the present.
7. The ideological change is mainly that of appreciating life quality (dwelling in situations of inherent worth) rather than adhering to an increasingly higher standard of living. There will be a profound awareness of the difference between big and great.
8. Those who subscribe to the foregoing points have an obligation directly or indirectly to participate in the attempt to implement the necessary changes.

Conclusion

There is disagreement about the role of developed and underdeveloped countries for increasing the different pollutions, diseases, deadly viruses etc. But it can say that the brutal killing of various species and the

uncontrolled immoral irresponsible scientific experimentation brings tragic consequences to the world. Sustainability incorporates with social, economic and environmental improvement. They all are mutually dependent. Economic and social development are not possible without healthy environment, same as sustainable development is impossible without economic and social development.

Today we realized that we have to be a responsible human being. No selfish person can exist alone in this world. We are interdependent. So we should follow the slogan 'live and together live' instead of 'either I or you'. Because if the people around me don't live or don't live well, I won't be able to live well for long either. From this realization it can be said that we are all connected to each other. We can live as an integrated part of the world. But not to be able to exist separate from it. And when we can save the interest of the whole world then naturally our own interests will be protected. We have to change and control the behaviours that harm others. We must stop the unwanted interference to the environment. The sustainable development ought to be established through unite of the humans of the society and other nonhuman worlds by combined of socio-political and economic development in a healthy environment. Through help and cooperation in financial, political, educational, etc., we will be able to build a healthy developed society, where humans and other entities in the environment will be recognized as moral being, who contains intrinsic/inherent value. Empathetic attitudes will help to eradicate of the caste, religion, gender hatred, war-mongering mentality etc. in the country. A beautiful healthy peaceful world will be created where we will be dependent on each other and live in mutual cooperation. It is mentioned in the book towards a "Second Generation" in Environmental Laws in the Asian and Pacific Region Select Trends *"The resilience of the community of life and the well-being of humanity depend upon preserving a healthy biosphere with all its ecological system, a rich variety of plants and animals, fertile soils, pure water and clean air. The global environment with its finite resource is a common function of all peoples. The protection of Earth's vitality, diversity and beauty is sacred trust."*⁸

We should follow deep ecological principles and change our man-centred ideology for establish realistic sustainability. We should minimize uses of natural resources and protect environment properly. If we believe that all members have intrinsic value and these values are not depend on human's interest then we can respect all members of the environment and to establish sustainability in true sense.

But we have to admit that only human activities are considering as moral practice. Morality, moral terms, moral criteria, good, bad, right, wrong every things are derived through humans brain, so we never refute human perspective in to the social policies, economic policies or environmental policies, because these all are made by humans. Non humans are not able to make any policies. They are unable to apply moral policies and activities. Therefore, minimal 'perspectival' anthropocentricity is unavoidable, human may get more opportunity in the world but humans should minimize and control their activities to non-human world.

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